

Human Trafficking Crime and Its Relation to Illegal Immigration in both International Agreements and Jordanian Legislation

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 04, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Human Trafficking; Illegal Immigration; Organized Crime, Palermo Protocol</p>	<p><i>This study tackled the issue of human trafficking and illegal immigration as stated in international agreements and national legislations. Light was shed on Jordanian legislation, subject of this study. The study aimed to discuss the concept of human trafficking and illegal immigration. The problem arises from the confusion between human trafficking and illegal immigrations, for the immigrant might be the victim of two crimes: trafficking and smuggling. The study concluded that each of these two concepts has its own meaning. Though they are different, yet they are confusing. The researchers came up with a criterion by which they could differentiate between trafficking and immigration, thus avoiding confusion. In addition, they elaborated on similarities and dissimilarities to clarify ambiguity.</i></p>
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Introduction

Human trafficking has been a very old issue. Throughout ancient times, there were individuals who were deprived of their rights and dignity and were traded in as if they were slaves. Only the lords were entitled to be called humans. Although such a thing is, by today's standards considered a crime, yet it was a style of life for the ancients.

Sabaki (2010) pointed out that lack of inhuman feelings, of conscience, and of morals in such lords, promoted that kind of crime because they only heeded for materialistic interest.

Human trafficking, as stated before, was found since creation in the form of slavery and exploitation. It later developed to human trafficking, the topic to be discussed in this study.

One of the forms of trafficking is illegal immigration that has increased recently. Exploiting the difficult conditions of humans was a major factor behind illegal immigration which was for the immigrants the ideal solution for the problems engulfing them.

Shinnawi (2014) mentioned that human trafficking is an international issue not limited to a certain state, but practicing this type of crime varies from one country to another pending on the way the countries perceive it and the way of combating it through legislations, agreements, and regulations.

Illegal immigration might overlap with trafficking, being one of the methods of trafficking through which the victims to be traded in will be transported from one country to another. Some individuals might love to illegally immigrate to another country in search for work though that might expose them to trafficking.

Sometimes, the human plans to achieve his goals legally or illegally by escaping from the terrific situation he lives under in his country. Such as situation provides a chance for the psychologically sick people to achieve illegal objectives by exploiting those victims in various ways which constitute human trafficking.

PARTS OF THE STUDY

The study is divided into the following parts:

First subject, nature of illegal immigration and human trafficking

First requisite, criterion of distinction between human trafficking and illegal immigrating

Second requisite, similarities between illegal immigration and trafficking

Second subject, methods of combating trafficking and illegal immigration and preventive measures to be taken

First requisite, combating human trafficking and illegal immigration in light of international agreements and Jordanian legislation

Second requisite, preventive procedures against trafficking and illegal immigration

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Problem of the study is incorporated in human trafficking that widely spread due to the bad economic, social and political conditions which led to the spread of such a kind of crime in which traffickers seized the opportunity to gain lots of money from victims. Jordan was the haven for varieties of refugees and war victims many of whom illegally entered the country. The problem lies in the correlation between human trafficking with illegal immigration which in reality confused regular courts at the end.

QUESTIONS OF THE STUDY

The questions that the study poses are:

- What is meant by human trafficking and illegal immigration?
- What does trafficking mean, according to Jordanian law of combating human trafficking?
- What are the ways of combating trafficking and what are the strategies to be adopted?
- Would victims of trafficking be indemnified?
- To what extent do enacted penalties deter trafficking?
- What is the range of compatibility between Jordan legislation in force with international agreements, regarding trafficking prevention and which to do if not?
- What is the criterion used to distinguish between human trafficking and illegal immigration?

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The importance of the study lies in tackling human trafficking in light of international agreements and national legislation, specifically the Jordanian type. Trafficking endangers society in general, threatens all classes, downgrades human dignity, and violates human rights.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aims to clarify the concepts of human trafficking and illegal immigration as stipulated in the Jordanian legislation for combating trafficking, in addition to the indemnity to be paid to the victim. It also clarifies the extent to which the set penalties deter such an act and the method used to discriminate illegal immigration from trafficking.

STUDY METHODOLOGY

The researchers used the descriptive analytical approach, the descriptive part to handle some study terms and the analytical to analyze legal provisions related to human trafficking and illegal immigration.

First topic: Illegal immigration and Human Trafficking

Shaikhali, (2009) pointed out that "Illegal immigration is one of the most dangerous phenomena that threaten international and national societies, being linked to crimes among which is human trafficking that globally ranks third after weapon trading and drugs. Though the two issues are distinctively stated in international and national legislations, yet illegal immigration might lead to human trafficking whenever the immigrant is illegally exploited.

Illegal immigration might overlap with trafficking through transporting the victims from one country to another. The person might illegally immigrate from one place to another in search for work, thus, becomes vulnerable to trafficking.

Individuals sometimes, immigrate seeking for work and other times escaping from oppression in their countries. Such a good rationale behind immigration provides people with sick minds an opportunity to trade in such people to gain money, thus become victims of human trafficking.

According to the UN Protocol (2000), both human trafficking and illegal immigration are considered crimes. But trafficking differs from immigration in that the former adopts bad means such as: cheating, recruiting, and coercion which sequentially end up with exploitation.

Illegal immigrant exposes himself to dangers of trafficking by agreeing with the smuggler to go ahead with the process of moving to the unknown, thus putting his future at the hand of that smuggler. Such acts oblige countries to take preventive measures to combat this type of crimes.

From what preceded, one finds common grounds between these two crimes, the most important of which are: interest, gaining money, and victim transfer. Such grounds make it difficult to determine the crime committed whether it is trafficking or illegal immigration.

Therefore, the researchers down here clarify the concepts of trafficking and illegal immigration as stipulated in international agreements and Jordanian legislations.

Article (3), item (1) of Palermo protocol defines human trafficking to be "recruiting persons, transferring them, providing shelters or taking them under duress in any form, kidnapping, cheating, exploiting their weakness, receiving money to get an approval from an authoritative person for exploitation.

The exploitation includes: prostitution, all types of sexual exploitation, slave labor, under duress services, slavery, enslavement or organ removal.

In article (3) of the Jordanian law number (9) 2009 for combating human trafficking crimes defined the crime to be: (1) attracting, transferring, sheltering people, or receiving them for the sake of exploitation under duress or by using power for coercion, kidnap, fraud, cheating, power abuse, giving or receiving sums of money, in order to get approval from the person who controls such people. (2) attracting, transferring, sheltering or receiving people under 18 years of age for the sake of exploitation even if that wasn't done under duress or under any of the methods stated in article (1) of this item. One can notice that though the definition of the Jordanian legislator for crimes of human trafficking is close to Palermo's provisions, there are still some minor differences such as using the term attracting instead of recruiting, besides the methods adopted in committing those crimes (Ruteimah, Wijdan, 2014,121).

The legislator had better refer to such methods because avoiding them might narrow down the type of this crime enabling criminals to escape punishment.

With reference to article (3/B) of the Jordanian law of preventing human trafficking (9). 2009, the Jordanian legislator provided a definite form of such crimes, contrary to what was stipulated on in Palermo Protocol 2000. That protocol stated "the crime minimally involves exploitation". Shamasneh (2019) pointed out that the Jordanian legislator failed to determine methods of exploitation as that might have dangerous reverberations. Consequently, human trafficking might take other forms never mentioned in this article such as: begging, for example. The legislator also excluded deportation or transfer from criminalization as stipulated on in Palermo Protocol of (2000).

As for illegal immigration, it is a cross-border crime as seen in the illegal move from one country to another. Such a move is risky for the immigrant who might be killed sinking or by shots from border guards. It also threatens security and peace of the sending and receiving countries.

Shaban (2017) said that illegal immigration is viewed differently from the perspective of states which immigrants leave and that the state that receives them. For the former, the concept involves a legitimate departure of any citizen from his country through illegal means or he might leave through a legitimate entrance, but by using forged identifications.

As for the latter, the country to which the immigrant legally or illegally arrives by sea or by land, he is given temporary residence permit. When he refuses to leave at the expiry date, he becomes illegal.

From what preceded, one can notice that human trafficking strongly correlates with illegal immigration. The researchers will highlight the criterion of distinction between them through the first requisite of this subject, and in the second they will tackle similarities between illegal immigration and human trafficking.

First requisite: Differences between crime of illegal immigration and human trafficking

(Mukhlafi, 2017; Bu Sqaieh, 2006) pointed out that with regard to the legal bases of the two crimes, the juridical one requires a criminal intent for exploitation of the victim in that crime, while illegal immigration only requires criminal intent.

Illegal immigration might change into trafficking whenever it leads to exploitation represented in the juridical aspect of trafficking through exploiting who helps the illegal immigrant against what was agreed upon with regard to crossing borders of a certain country.

Irteimah (2014) indicated that human trafficking is a crime of assault on the human, while in illegal immigration the assault is on laws of the sending and receiving countries to which and out of which the illegal immigrant moves. Based on that, the exploited to be traded in will be the victim, while the illegal immigrant will be just a defendant before competent authorities.

According to U.N (2006) trafficking could be within the boundaries of the same country, while immigration is an illegal crossing between countries.

The relation between the immigrant and smuggler is a profit relationship that ends at the immigrant's arrival to his destination and smuggler's getting money, but the relation between the trafficker and the victim is constant because the former gains money through exploiting his victim in different ways.

In addition, in illegal immigration the immigrant sometimes resorts to the smuggler to agree on the transfer method, but in trafficking, there is no need for such an agreement as the trading process is effected through fraud or cheating (Burk Carolyn, n.d).

Therefore, illegal immigration changes into trafficking through the smuggler's use of one of trafficking elements, cheating and fraud. Even after crossing borders, immigrants might be exposed to coercion, cheating or fraud, thus becoming victims of trafficking.

Second requisite: similarities between illegal immigration and human trafficking

Both the immigrant and the victim are mostly exposed to death for the former might sink and die or may be sacrificed with by the smuggler for security reasons. The latter might also die through the process of extracting any of his organs, besides sexual exploitation (Irteimah, 2014: 17).

The major objective for both the trafficker and the smuggler is to gain profit by exploiting the immigrant and victims. (UN, 2006:2).

Human trafficking through crossing borders occurs in ways similar to those of immigration by using forged travel documents, fraud, or by sea boats. Thus, the two are cross border acts. Traffickers might themselves be the smugglers (U.N for immigration, 2020:3).

From what preceded one can conclude that the criterion of distinction between illegal immigration and human trafficking is the objective and the consent.

Sometimes, it is difficult to distinguish between the two crimes, mainly, at first stages. Therefore, competent authority should clarify to borders' officials the principles and concepts upon which each crime rests.

Second Subject: Ways to combat human trafficking and illegal immigration and measures to prevent them

As illegal immigration and trafficking represent danger at the national and international levels, legislators showed great concern about such crimes trying to stop or limit their spread to avert the damages they might cause to national and international communities.

Al-Sabki (2010) pointed out that both international community and national legislators adopted several ways to combat such crimes. Therefore, international communities ratified relevant agreements and protocols concerned with trafficking and illegal immigration combat, while national legislators enacted laws that conform to international ratified agreements regarding combat of such crimes. An example of that is Jordan which enacted law (9), 2009 against trafficking. That law conforms to (UN) agreement to combat organized crime and agrees with the addended protocol for the prevention and punishment of human trafficking.

Al-Sabki added that because such crimes endanger peace and security of communities, they must take necessary measures to protect themselves from the destructive dangers of these crimes by: promoting awareness in the groups targeted by smugglers and traffickers, controlling borders, real estates and any other things that might be used in such kind of crimes. In addition, non-governmental organizations that play an effective role in preventing such crimes should be supported through giving constant awareness courses to the target groups.

This subject will be divided into two requisites: the first will focus on trafficking and illegal immigration in light of international agreements and Jordanian judiciary, the second will discuss ways of preventing these two acts.

First requisite: combating human trafficking and illegal immigration in light of international agreements and Jordanian legislation

In this part of the study, the researchers discuss national and international efforts exerted to combat such crimes, by elaborating on relevant international agreements besides national legislation enacted against these crimes.

Part one: International efforts exerted in combating crimes of trafficking and illegal immigration

The two crimes were of great concern for many countries which concluded several international agreements whose major purpose is to combat such crimes that threaten both communities, national and international (Shinnaw, 2014: 411).

Among the foremost regional and international agreements concluded to combat these crimes are:

First: The United Nations agreements to fight organized crime through complementary national laws and protocols that prevent and punish trafficking, especially with women and children, held in Palermo, Italy, 2001.

This agreement includes the foremost international instruments relevant to crimes of human trafficking and illegal immigrations en masse. According to this instrument, all countries concerned need to take necessary measures to prevent and combat trafficking, especially with women and children. Such a thing obligates the states to enact laws to punish traffickers and to secure the internationally acknowledged basic human rights (Palermo protocol, 2).

It is worth mentioning that there is no comprehensive international instrument that covers all aspects of trafficking which eventually make the victims feel insecure.

In compliance with provisions of article (9) of the protocol, all state parties shall use special ways to prevent trafficking by taking necessary measures and policies to prevent such a crime. This can be achieved by: conducting necessary research, initiating social and economic measures, and adopting policies that encourage cooperation with any relevant non-governmental organizations. State members are also requested to consolidate bi-or multilateral cooperation that eases burden of poverty, backwardness, and lack of equal opportunities on the victims, specially children and women. In addition, social, educational, and cultural measures need also to be taken to combat such a crime (Article 9,4).

From what preceded, one can conclude that the major objective of the protocol is to consolidate cooperation among state members to combat trafficking, in addition to securing and maintaining the victims internationally acknowledged basic right as stipulated in the protocol.

Regarding protection of trafficking victims, article (6) of the protocol stipulated on helping them through following:

- 1- Protecting victims' personal freedom and maintaining confidentiality regarding the measures taken by state parties.
- 2- States parties must enact internal legislations to protect humans from trafficking by giving them the right of defense and necessary assistance to present their ideas and to take criminal procedures against traffickers.
- 3- Providing homes to cater for these victims in order to recover, in addition to secure teaching centers and to provide psychiatric care for them.
- 4- States parties must take into consideration age and gender, especially the needs of children and women who are the weakest part in the society.
- 5- The states also need to guarantee, through internal legislations, victims' indemnification for the damages caused by their crime.

Article (10) of the protocol ascertained that state parties, to combat the crime, should cooperate through exchanging information via internal enacted laws by which they could detect those who crossed the borders by forged documents or through no documents, being victims or traffickers. The states should also exchange experiences regarding the ways criminals use for human trafficking.

Second: European council agreement

The agreement aims to prevent and combat human trafficking. Helping victims of trafficking and establishing equality between the two sexes are among its major objectives. That was contrary to Palermo Protocol provisions which paid more attention to care for women and children. The agreement also aims at taking effective trial and investigating measures. In addition, it focuses on cooperation between countries as that plays an important role in combating the crime which sequentially dictates applying rules to protect human rights in compliance with the principle of non-discrimination on basis of religion, language, gender, and color (European council agreements, 2005, (1) 197).

Regional and international agreements to combat illegal immigration

First: Shengen agreement

It is one of the European council agreements to combat illegal immigration. The agreement stipulates that states should exchange personal information via a database system (sis) set for such a purpose to control borders and to make the job easier. Information exchange could be done through the national networks affiliated with the central system. Such an act makes it easier to arrest illegal immigrants and limit tricky ways used to enter those states (Bu Azizah, 2019, (2) 751).

Part two: Efforts made in Jordanian legislation to combat human trafficking and illegal immigration

According to Olwan, (2019: (3) 325), the Jordanian legislator adopted several ways to combat trafficking starting with Jordanian constitution that protects freedoms, compels nobody to work, arrests any person or restricts freedom, except in accordance with provisions of Jordanian law.

Jordan ratified several anti-trafficking agreements such as: U.N agreements to combat organized crime through national protocols. Jordan confirms that the ratified international agreements are more compelling than national laws whenever any disagreement emerges between the two legislations (Tamkeen Center, 2016). Jordan has also enacted a special law for the prevention of trafficking; law No. 9, 2009, a national committee to combat trafficking was also formed in compliance with article (4). More than that Jordan put down anti-trafficking strategies. Several non-governmental societies, like Tamkeen, which provide legal assistance and defends victims, came to existence (Tamkeen, 2016).

Article no. (9) of 2009 law determined the deterrent punishment for this crime. The legislator distinguished between responsibility of the normal and corporate persons. It also elaborated on severe punishment included in that article.

Article (8) of the law stipulated that any trafficker shall be imprisoned or penalized to pay a fine of 1000-5000 Jordanian dinars or for both when he commits trafficking crime, in accordance with clause (1), item (1), article (3) of that law.

The Jordanian legislator criminalized any act affiliated with trafficking such as: not reporting about plans for this crime or hiding its effects. These are considered offences not radical felonies. The law didn't authorize the court to exempt non reporters if they were the criminal's offspring, wife, or brothers. Regarding responsibility of the corporate person, the Jordan legislator, in the law of trafficking prevention, put down deterrent penalties like fines or work suspense temporarily or permanently. In doing so, the law complies with UN agreement for combating organized crime which stipulates in its tenth article that the corporate person is held accountable. Thus, both Jordanian legislation and Palermo agreement adopted dual punishment which entails that corporate responsibility doesn't affect criminalization of normal traffickers.

During the last few years, Jordanian courts examined 275 cases of human trafficking which constituted 25% of annual cases. It is noted that the number of examined cases after instituting trafficking combat unit in 2012 increased. 50% of cases of criminals filed to courts were convicted.

Due to high fees of cases, the victim won't be able to file a case of indemnity for the material and corporate damages to which he was subjected. It is noted that litigation fees are (3%) for the first one thousand Jordanian dinars, (2%) for the second thousand, and (1%) for the third.

Jordanian legislator followed the track of UN agreement in criminalizing attempts of trafficking pursuant to article (5) provision which criminalized such an act. But the law of trafficking prevention didn't include any provision related to trafficking attempts. Since the Jordanian law of punishment didn't criminalize offence attempt except for what was specifically stipulated on, it criminalized attempts of crimes. Pursuant to that, the crimes with provisions stipulated on in article (9) 2009 of trafficking prevention law are punishable with regard to attempt.

A unit for the prevention of human trafficking affiliated with public security department was instituted in order to combat the crime. That could be done through investigating relevant crimes and those suspected to be trafficking; besides accepting victims' complaints which were forwarded to the public prosecutor who refers them to the competent court.

A liason officer was assigned for airports and sheltering homes in order to facilitate voluntary return of victims. In addition, awareness sessions were held for airport employees. The role of liason officer for sheltering homes is to ensure that medical and psychological helps were provided and that the victim was empowered to avoid trafficking again (Tarawneh, Basel. 2018:1).

The following table explains Jordan's ways of combating human trafficking

Ways of combating human trafficking in Jordan	
1- International agreements on combating trafficking	The kingdom ratified several international agreements and protocols for combating trafficking. Therefore, national legislations followed the tracks of international counterparts, especially that of UN for combating organized crimes and supplementary protocols. The kingdom has ratified most of the major agreements concluded by UN.
2- National legislations	The constitution confirmed personal freedom for everyone and every assault on that is considered a crime punishable by law. It also secured constitutional protection against coercive work and never enforced compulsory labor.
3- Laws	Anti-human trafficking No. (9) whose aim is to combat and eradicate it.
4- Legislations relevant to human trafficking	Law no. (9), 1996 prevents transferring home and agriculture laborers to another employer without a new contract signed in the presence of an employee of ministry of labor because such workers are the most susceptible for trafficking.
5- Regulations by which homes to shelter trafficking victims are established so as to protect them and to provide social, psychological and medical assistance to them as well. Children and women are separated from adults and men. Nobody is allowed to enter women's places without consent of the director or the competent employee.	1- Part of family reconciliation centers in Amman and Irbid are assigned to home trafficking victims. The centers started accepting them on August, 2014. 2- Al-Karama Home which belongs to the Ministry of Social Development was established on July 14, 2015.
6- National committee for combating human trafficking	Pursuant to article (4) of combating human trafficking law, the committee was instituted to achieve four objectives: (protection, prevention, prosecution, and companies building) The prosecution is conducted through a branch for combating human trafficking in the department of criminal investigation in general security directorate. The committee is concerned with consolidating national, regional, and international cooperation through adopting certain mechanisms to exchange experiences and information.

With regard to illegal immigration, the Jordanian legislator didn't enact any law to combat trafficking, but was satisfied with Jordanian general law and ratification of protocols of immigrants' smuggling by air, sea, and land, a supplementary of combating organized crime through the national law of 2009. A provision in article (153) of punishment law stipulates that anyone who illegally enters the kingdom should be punished. That contrasts with what the Egyptian legislator did in enacting a special law to combat illegal immigration and

immigrants' smuggling. It is hoped that the Jordanian legislator follows the tracks of his Egyptian counterpart to enact a special relevant law against illegal immigration which endangers individuals and the state itself for it impacts national economy.

Second requisite: Preventive measures against human trafficking and illegal immigration

International agreements and national legislations identify the crime and its pillars which are punishable according to law. They both combat human trafficking and illegal immigration in several ways. Preventive and combat measures are not responsibility of governments only, but of people as well who should take numerous ways to protect themselves from dangers ensuing from such crimes.

Prevention is the basic element to protect human rights and maintain societal security. It is as important as any international movement that combats human trafficking and illegal immigration. It, thus, enables victims to repulse dangers ensuing from such crimes.

Prevention also immunizes society against tactics of traffickers and smugglers through spreading awareness among the targeted groups by which they could distinguish cheating and fraud adopted by traffickers.

Prevention ways will be elaborated on in this requisite as follows:

First: preventive measures against human trafficking

There are several strategies that governments need to take to eradicate trafficking that relies on supply and demand, besides traffickers.

Prevention against supply

This type of prevention starts through disseminating awareness and culture in societies about this crime and the methods adopted by traffickers exemplified in recruitment, cheating, and fraud. Through awareness, the individual would be able to distinguish the crime before it occurs. Thus, providing work opportunities, education system and awareness will secure individuals from being victimized (office of monitoring and combating trafficking).

Prevention against demand

This can be achieved through tracing gangs and individuals who exploit victims and by suing them to court. In addition, traffickers' names should be publicized, inflict severe punishment on them, monitor them, and proclaim names of employers who impose coercive labor so as to deter them (Ayyad, Hani, 2016).

Prevention against traffickers

Hariri, (2019) pointed out that to prevent traffickers from committing their crimes, a set of measures need to be taken: to load preventive programs on the web network that help track traffickers, competent security bodies should identify trafficking lines, to exchange information between countries with regard to passport to punish official employees who facilitate trafficking and finally to rigidly enforce national laws to deter them.

Signatories of Palermo Protocol should abide by preventive measures stipulated on in articles (9, 11, 12) which necessitate that research and media campaigns need to be taken. In addition, bilateral accords need to be concluded, societal cooperation should be done, and border measures by which traffickers could be detected need also to be considered. Moreover, states should reject granting visas to those involved in such crimes, commercial transport companies should also be band from working with traffickers.

There are also other preventive measures related to home servants, which could be of benefit if used appropriately. These preventive measures might be gained through teaching those servants the language of the country in which they will be employed via their embassies or through recruitment agencies. This way, those servants would be able to defend their rights and the judiciary can easily handle any crime when it occurs, as translation most often is not exact.

Second: Preventive ways against illegal immigration

There are numerous preventive ways against illegal immigration that both exporting and importing countries should take. These measures which have to be taken by people and the state combined might be: social, economic, and legal.

Social and economic measures

Preventive measures against immigration starts in the family where the individual is brought up. The family should teach their children, secure peace and stability by avoiding family problems. The school has a role to play as well through inculcating national identity in children through education programs that consolidate feelings of citizenship and sense of belonging (Burkan, Fayzeh, 2016).

There is no doubt that providing basics for individuals plays a role in preventing immigration. These basics are: housing, health insurance, education, exploiting youth qualifications by investing them in education

clubs, institutions, and societies, thus creating jobs for them. Once these are secured, youth never think of immigration caused by material difficulties they live under (Raghib, Nabeel, 2004: 2.67).

Legal measures

In addition to combating crime, states shoulder responsibility of taking preventive measures achieved by interlinking security and media bodies to create such measures. Names of criminals and methods of combating crimes should be promulgated. The objective behind the promulgation is orientation, learning lessons, and achieving self-security. It also acquaints individuals with the crime, in addition to penalties inflicted on criminals (Burkan, Fayzeh: 2016, 3. 103).

What preceded reveals that countries need to intensify border security measures and to enact deterrent laws against traffickers. They should also eradicate favoritism, enforce equality and justice, and prepare courses and programs to enable security bodies to detect such crimes and the dangers that might result from this phenomenon.

Conclusion

In summary, one can see that the current study is important because it interlinks two dangerous phenomena which differ in concept, characteristics, and motives. Despite this difference, yet human trafficking and illegal immigration can be blended.

Throughout the study, the researchers illustrated the two concepts in light of international agreements among which are: UN agreement for combating organized crimes through national year 2000, supplementary protocols. In addition, due to the danger that each phenomenon represents which becomes more serious once combined, national and international efforts should be orchestrated and coordinated to combat human trafficking and illegal immigration in order to eliminate their negative impacts that threaten national and international stability.

They also endanger victims' lives. Therefore, such crimes should be tracked to enable governments to take protective measures to ensure community safety.

Though qualities, forms, and reasons for human trafficking and illegal immigration differ, yet they overlap. When the illegal immigrants end up with exploitation by traffickers through fraud and deception by which the victims are handed in to specialized gangs that extract their body organs, or through imposing coercive labor on them. Thus, illegal immigration turns into human trafficking.

Findings of the study

The study came up to the following results:

- 1- Human trafficking is top of the list for the whole world as it endangers national and international communities. Many of them led to several crimes the foremost of which is illegal immigration that is as dangerous as trafficking because it endangers national and international security and stability.
- 2- Consent doesn't count in human trafficking because the victim, in that case, doesn't have any option, but to give in, while illegal immigration consent is taken into account because the person accepts to illegally enter another country.
- 3- Trafficking is a crime that threatens person's health and safety, while illegal immigration threatens security of states. Trafficking crime requires a special criminal intent typified by exploitation, besides a general criminal one, while immigration requires general criminal intent.
- 4- Illegal immigration requires that the immigrant sometimes has to resort to the smuggler to agree on the way to be transferred by, i.e., by his consent, but trafficking lacks victim's consent because it happens through fraud and deception.
- 5- Reasons behind trafficking and immigration may be social, economic, or political. The immigrant immigrates illegally because of complications of legal immigration measures in developed countries. Poverty pushes victims of trafficking to do dangerous deeds to secure a livelihood, thus become susceptible for exploitation by traffickers.
- 6- National provisions concerned with combating trafficking and immigration are not enough; the increase in these phenomena proves that.
- 7- The Hashemite kingdom provides care for trafficking victims as seen in establishing homes for them like family conciliation home in Amman and Irbid, besides Al-Karama house which provides psychological and health care for them.

Recommendations

Based on the preceding findings, the study recommends the following:

- 1- To enact national laws that comply with international agreements to combat illegal immigration.
- 2- To put down mechanisms to combat trafficking and illegal immigration by adopting the following: exchange experiences, construct worldwide centers to educate and enlighten people on such crimes, hold national and

international conferences to discuss causes and solutions, and finally consolidate cooperation between countries through which traffickers and illegal immigrants pass.

3- To improve economic conditions, to provide job opportunities, and to facilitate legal immigration measures in order to avoid the illegal type, and to give courses, to home servants, in the language of the employing country so as to be able to defend themselves.

4- To adopt a mechanism to use electronic and travel documents because such a thing plays an effective role in detecting fake documents.

5- To enforce deterrent penalties against trafficking and illegal immigration as a means of protection against such crimes.

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